

Concrete curing monitoring using polymer optical fibre Bragg grating sensors

A. Pospori^{*a}, A. Ioannou^a, J. Melo^b, P. Antunes^c, H. Varum^b, C.A.F. Marques^c, K. Kalli^a

^a Photonics and Optical Sensors Research Laboratory, Cyprus University of Technology, Saripolou 33, 3036, Limassol, Cyprus

^b CONSTRUCT-LESE, Faculty of Engineering (FEUP), University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

^c I3N & Physics Department, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

ABSTRACT

A novel prototype sensing device based on polymer (CYTOP-XYLEX) optical fibre Bragg grating sensors was developed to monitor temperature and relative humidity levels of reinforced concrete from its initial curing phase to a prolonged period. The prototype can be used for concrete quality control offering numerous advantages, such as small size, robustness, high sensitivity, and low-cost continuous in-situ measurements.

Keywords: Polymer optical fibre, fibre Bragg grating sensors, concrete curing, temperature, relative humidity

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous monitoring of concrete quality from its initial curing phase to a prolonged period is a powerful management tool for general safety and maintenance strategies. Structural health monitoring systems are typically composed of sensors based on electrical transducers, which are large in size and suffer from significant noise levels¹. Alternatively, optical fibre sensors have immunity to electromagnetic interference and corrosion, small size, low weight, high fatigue limits, and multiplexing capabilities^{1,2}. A single fibre with multiple sensors along its length can be incorporated into tight areas of structural components and in structures having a span of several kilometres. Polymer optical fibre (POF) sensors can offer additional advantages over the standard silica optical fibres, such as enhanced stress/pressure sensitivity due to the lower Young's modulus, higher strain limits, higher bending flexibility and higher fracture toughness³. The characteristics of polymeric materials render POF sensors ideal for embedding them in other structures for structural health monitoring⁴. Hydrophilic POFs can also detect relative humidity (RH)⁵, which is a critical parameter for concrete structures' quality control and quality assurance. During the concrete curing process, the temperature and moisture levels change due to the hydration reaction – a chemical exothermic reaction between cement and water, which releases various chemicals and heat, contributing to the strengthening of concrete⁶. Properly concrete curing involves maintenance of desired moisture and temperature conditions for continued hydration process for the development of strength and durability⁶.

In this work, a prototype sensing device based on polymer optical fibre Bragg grating (POFBG) sensors is demonstrated, which can be used to detect in-situ temperature and moisture levels of reinforced concrete from its early stage curing process to a prolonged period. The novel POF used for the prototype sensor has a CYTOP⁷ (amorphous perfluoropolymer) core and a XYLEX⁸ (blend of polycarbonate and polyester) over-cladding. The CYTOP material was developed to tackle the high optical loss exhibited by the standard poly(methyl methacrylate) optical fibres. XYLEX is used as over-cladding because it offers enhanced chemical resistance and impact strength⁸. Another characteristic of XYLEX is its high water absorptivity⁸, which is 0.50%, compared with CYTOP, which has less than 0.01% water absorptivity⁷. Due to the hydrophilic nature of XYLEX, the POFBG sensors can be used to detect moisture levels in concrete. The proposed prototype sensing device consists of a single POF with an array of 2 POFBG sensors. The first POFBG sensor was encapsulated into a stainless-steel needle for temperature monitoring only. The second sensor was encapsulated into a plastic tube with holes for temperature and RH detection. The reason for encapsulating the sensors is to avoid any pressure applied to sensors from the concrete because the Bragg wavelength shift of the POFBG sensor can also be affected by pressure-induced changes. The prototype sensing device demonstrates the ability to continuously monitor in-situ temperature and moisture levels in reinforced concrete structures for quality control purposes.

*andreas.pospori@cut.ac.cy; orcid.org/0000-0003-4866-1361

2. FABRICATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF PROTOTYPE

Before the fabrication of POFBG sensors, the POF was annealed at 70 °C temperature and 40% humidity for 4 hours in a climatic chamber to improve the sensors' performance⁹. The array of 2 POFBG sensors was fabricated in a custom-made polymer optical fibre (GigaPOF Custom Fibre 250/20, Chromis Fiberoptics). The POF has a CYTOP graded-index core with 20 ± 4 μm diameter and a XYLEX over-cladding with 250 ± 5 μm diameter. The sensors were inscribed using a femtosecond laser system (High Q laser femtoREGEN) with 517 nm operating wavelength, 2 kHz repetition rate, 220 fs pulse duration, and 20 nJ pulse energy. The 2 POFBG sensors were inscribed with the plane-by-plane method¹⁰, in which the laser beam is focused into the CYTOP core through XYLEX over-cladding using an objective length of 50x magnification and 0.42 NA (Mitutoyo). Each POFBG was fabricated by inscribing 850 Bragg planes with 5 μm width to obtain a single-peak reflection spectrum¹⁰.

After the fabrication of POFBG sensors, each fibre was connectorised with a standard silica optical fibre for interrogation purposes. The connectorisation was performed by using the butt-coupled technique with a UV adhesive. After the fabrication of 2 POFBG sensors, the POFBG 1 was strained 0.36% and adhered into a stainless-steel needle (gauge 23 – internal diameter of 330 μm) using a Norland Optical Adhesive 63. The POFBG 2 was placed into a plastic tube with multiple holes of 640 μm diameter. The plastic tube and stainless-steel needle were adhered onto a 16-mm reinforcing bar, as shown in Figure 1.

After the adhesives were set, the temperature and RH sensitivity characterisation of the two sensors was performed in a climatic chamber (Mettler HCP 108). The 85 cm long reinforcing bar was placed through the side holes of the climatic chamber. To investigate the response due to temperature changes, the RH was kept constant at $40\pm 1\%$, and the temperature was changed in steps of 5°C from 30°C to 45°C. To assess RH sensitivity, the temperature was kept constant at 30°C, and the RH was varied in steps of 10%RH from 40%-70%RH. As shown in Figure 2, POFBG 1 has only temperature sensitivity, and POFBG 2 is sensitive to both temperature and RH variations. The results from the POFBG 1 sensor can be used to compensate the temperature variations induced in the POFBG 2 sensor to calculate the RH level. From the response of sensors, the calculated temperature sensitivities of POFBG 1 and POFBG 2 are -48 ± 1 $\text{pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ and 18 ± 1 $\text{pm}/^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The vast difference in sensitivities along the same POF is because the POFBG 1 was pre-strained to enhance its temperature sensitivity (switching also to a negative sensitivity) – a method demonstrated recently⁹. The RH sensitivity for POFBG 2 is 12 ± 1 $\text{pm}/\%RH$, and there is no RH sensitivity in POFBG 1.

Figure 1: Design of prototype sensing device.

Figure 2: Temperature and RH response of POFBG sensors.

3. MONITORING CONCRETE CURING

The reinforcing bar with the attached POFBG sensors was positioned at the centre of the 20x20x20 cm³ casting mould. Using an interrogation system (Micron Optics HYPERION), the peak position of sensors was automatically captured every minute. The POFBG sensors started monitoring temperature and RH 45 minutes before the concrete was poured into the mould. Then, a concrete grade C25/30 was prepared and immediately poured into the mould, containing the reinforcing bar and the sensors, which continued the monitoring. The Bragg wavelength peaks were continuously tracked for 96 hours from the moment when the concrete was poured. The Bragg wavelength shift of POFBG 1 and POFBG 2 sensors is depicted in Figure 3(a). Considering the sensitivities of sensors obtained from their characterisation test, their Bragg wavelength shift can be converted to calculated temperature and RH levels, as shown in Figure 3(b).

Figure 3: (a) Bragg wavelength shift of POFBG sensors, and (b) calculated in-situ temperature and RH of concrete during initial curing.

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, a prototype sensing device using novel CYTOP-XYLEX POFBG sensors is developed for monitoring the reinforced concrete structure from its initial curing phase to a prolonged period. The POFBG sensors attached to the reinforcing bar can detect the in-situ temperature and relative humidity of concrete, which are critical parameters defining the quality and durability of the structure. The prototype is small in size, robust, highly sensitive to measurements and can offer continuous monitoring during the entire lifetime of the concrete structure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to these results has received funding from the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions - Individual Fellowships) under REA grant agreement No. 844618 (project POSPORI). This work is also funded by the research project INTEGRATED/0918/0031 (LightSense Project) by the Republic of Cyprus through the Research and Innovation Foundation and European Development Fund and the Cyprus University of Technology. This paper also reports research developed under financial support provided by “FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia”, Portugal, co-funded by the European Social Fund, namely through the post-doc fellowship of José Melo, with reference SFRH/BPD/115352/2016 and by Base Funding - UIDB/04708/2020 and Programmatic Funding - UIDP/04708/2020 of the CONSTRUCT - Instituto de I&D em Estruturas e Construções - funded by national funds through the FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) relatively to the authors José Melo and Humberto Varum. This work was also supported by FCT/MCTES and FCT/MEC through national funds and when applicable co-funded EU funds under the projects UIDB/50025/2020-UIDP/50025/2020 and grants CEECINST/00026/2018 and 2021.00667.CEECIND.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sakiyama, F. I. H., Lehmann, F., and Garrecht, H., "Structural health monitoring of concrete structures using fibre-optic-based sensors: A review," *Magazine of concrete research* 73(4), 174-194 (2021).
- [2] Li, H. N., Li, D. S., and Song, G. B., "Recent applications of fiber optic sensors to health monitoring in civil engineering," *Engineering structures* 26(11), 1647-1657 (2004).
- [3] Min, R., Ortega, B., and Marques, C., "Latest Achievements in Polymer Optical Fiber Gratings: Fabrication and Applications," *Photonics* 6(2), 36 (2019).
- [4] Kuang, K. S. C., Quek, S. T., Koh, C. G., Cantwell, W. J., and Scully, P. J., "Plastic optical fibre sensors for structural health monitoring: A review of recent progress," *Journal of sensors* (2009).
- [5] Webb, D. J., "Fibre Bragg grating sensors in polymer optical fibres," *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 26(9), 092004 (2015).
- [6] Schindler, A. K., *Concrete hydration, temperature development, and setting at early-ages*, The University of Texas at Austin (2002).
- [7] "CYTOP Technical Information," AGC Chemicals Europe, <<https://www.Agcce.com/Cytop-Technical-Information>> (11 January 2023).
- [8] "Xylex resin," SABIC, <<https://www.sabic.com/en/products/polymers/xylex-resins/xylex-resin>> (11 January 2023).
- [9] Pospori, A., Ioannou, A., and Kalli, K. "Temperature and Humidity Sensitivity of Polymer Optical Fibre Sensors Tuned by Pre-Strain," *Sensors* 22(19), 7233 (2022).
- [10] Theodosiou, A., Lacraz, A., Stassis, A., Koutsides, C., Komodromos, M. and Kalli, K., "Plane-by-plane femtosecond laser inscription method for single-peak Bragg gratings in multimode CYTOP polymer optical fiber," *J. Light. Technol.* 35(24), 5404-5410 (2017).